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NMR STRUCTURAL-GROUP CHARACTERISTICS AND DETAILED SHIFT RANGES IN LIGHT, HEAVY AND CATALYZED OILS

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Abstract

Application of high resolution ^{13}C nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) spectroscopy to characterize of light, heavy and catalyzed oils was demonstrated. Molar fractions of primary, secondary, quaternary, tertiary, aromatic groups, aromatic factor and average hydrocarbon chain length of aliphatic hydrocarbons of these oil samples according to ^{13}C NMR spectra were determined. The received parameters indicate about the success of the catalytic treatment of the studied heavy oil sample. The detailed assignment of the ^{13}C NMR signals and their comparison between light, heavy and catalyzed oil samples were carried out. Changes in the chemical shifts of the ^{13}C NMR signals upon a detailed study of the spectra also confirm the positive effect of catalytic treatment of studied sample.

Keywords: ^{13}C NMR spectroscopy; heavy oil; oil fraction; functional group; qualitative analysis; quantitative composition; aromaticity; attached proton test; gated decoupling.

1. Introduction

The characterization of crude oil and related products is of increasing interest to the scientific community and the petroleum industry because the property and composition of samples from different oilfields are different. In this regard, various spectroscopic methods find their application.

^{13}C nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) spectroscopy has recently become increasingly popular as a tool for studying the characteristics of natural raw materials and their individual organic compounds ([1]; [2]; [3, 6942-6946]; [4, 1-9]; [5, 2858-2864]; [6, 117622]; [7, 597-598]). NMR spectroscopy is used to study various petrochemical objects, expanding the possibilities for research in the field of geological and chemical problems ([8, 423-473]; [9]).

There are some important advantages and disadvantages regarding this analytical technique ([10, 464-475]; [11, 18-37]).

The advantages are a reduction in the time taken for the analysis, and that it is a rapid and non-invasive process. Moreover, by using NMR, it is possible to analyze the chemical nature of individual types of hydrogen and carbon atoms, in various and complex mixtures of petroleum and in the final products obtained by refining processes. In the NMR spectra, the functional groups of aromatics, aliphatics, and olefins can be fixed; accordingly, it is possible to differentiate a polynuclear aromatic from mononuclear aromatic and to identify the fuel physical properties by the concentration of aromatics and the chain length of aliphatics.

Among the disadvantages of NMR spectroscopy the following can be noted: the high cost, the risk of magnetic disturbances, requiring magnetic shielding, and the overlap of frequency ranges, complex information, and requirement of statistical approach to correlate the spectral data with the characterization of crude oil.

^1H NMR spectroscopy can be applied in the characterization and identification of crude oil fractions, and it is a suitable way to predict the total hydrogen content as well as the distribution of hydrogen among functional groups present in the crude. Furthermore, information about the structural characteristics can be obtained by this method in order to estimate the molecular weight and to analyze the effects in several refining processes. On the other side, suitable information about the molecular carbon skeleton can be obtained by ^{13}C NMR. This NMR technique is important for the structure elucidation and chemical composition of a sample. In addition, it distinguishes the existence of quaternary carbons of many functional groups, and produces spectra with well quality. For this reason, ^{13}C NMR has become one of the most important methods in the analysis of crude oil fractions.

NMR has been used in the analysis of heavy petroleum fractions in many researches ([12, 280-281]; [13, 111-120]; Bansal et al., 1998 [14, 1223-1227]; [15, 81-86]; [16, 151-123]). The main purpose was to help refineries to refine heavy crude oils more efficiently and at low processing costs.

Actually, because of the complex mixture of compounds in crude oil, applying suitable and professional techniques to improve the quality of the NMR spectra and to obtain better quantitative information about the sample in analysis are crucial. Therefore, beyond the use of one-dimensional NMR spectroscopy (^1H and ^{13}C NMR), it is more suitable to use the "spectral editing" techniques. The use of the "spectral editing" techniques demonstrates great potentialities in structural elucidation and quantification of complex mixtures to improve the analysis of the ^1H and ^{13}C NMR spectra, owing to the overlapping of the signals. The aim of these "spectral editing" techniques is to participate to the separation of primary (CH_3), secondary (CH_2), tertiary (CH),

and quaternary carbons and to a sensitivity improvement. Some of "spectral editing" techniques are used in this work: Attached Proton Test (APT) and ^{13}C NMR Gated Decoupling (GD) experiments. These methods also known as polarization transfer methods. The aim of these methods is to transfer the large excess polarization of the ^1H to the insensitive ^{13}C nuclei before its perturbation.

The objective of this work is to carried out the comparison between light, heavy and catalyzed oil samples: obtaining their structural-group characteristics and the complete ^{13}C NMR chemical shift assignments.

2. Materials and methods

NMR experiments on studied oil samples were performed on a Bruker Avance III HD 700 NMR spectrometer. The studied oil sample was diluted with deuterated chloroform. Field lock and shimming were achieved using the deuterium signal from CDCl_3 solvent.

^{13}C NMR spectra were recorded using 90° pulses with broadband proton decoupling (pulse program

zgig); relaxation delay between consecutive accumulations were 3.3 s (and acquisition time was 2.3 s); spectrum width was set to 220.0 ppm; number of scans was 1300. Exponential digital filter with the LB parameter of 10 Hz was applied prior to Fourier transformation. Measurements were made at the temperature of 25°C . All the NMR spectra were integrated after baseline correction, and a mean of minimum three integration values has been taken for each calculation. The relative standard deviation of the results of manual integration did not exceed 3%.

3. Structural-group characterization and comparison of light, heavy and catalyzed oils by high resolution ^{13}C NMR spectroscopy

The group analysis method can be used to determine the oil composition, wherein the composition is expressed as relative quantities of different types of molecules, such as aromatic molecules, olefins, alkanes, and cycloalkanes and their numerous isomeric analogues. Oil fractions can be described as the average ratio of structural groups (Table 1).

Table 1.

Distribution of ^{13}C NMR chemical shifts of functional groups defining the composition of oil samples [17].

^{13}C NMR chemical shifts range, ppm	Organic functional group
11.0–12.5	γ - CH_3 -groups and some CH - and CH_2 - groups in aromatic fragments, CH_3 - group in ethyl-substituted cyclohexane
12.5–15.0	γ - CH_3 - (and more distant) methyl groups of aromatic cycle; CH_3 - group, shielded by two neighboring aromatic rings
15.0–18.0	β - CH_3 - substituent in ethylene group
18.0–20.5	α - CH_3 - group, shielded by one aromatic; some α - CH_3 - and CH_2 - groups in hydroaromatic and naphthenic fragments
20.5–22.5	α - CH_3 - group, unshielded by aromatic; some α - CH_3 - and CH_2 - groups in hydroaromatic and naphthenic fragments
22.5–24.0	γ - CH_2 - and CH_3 -groups; β - CH_2 - groups in unsubstituted tetralin structures
24.0–27.5	methylene (CH_2) groups in naphthenic fragments; α - CH - and β - CH_2 - groups in a propyl and indan fragments; β - CH_3 - group in isopropyl
27.5–37.0	methylene (CH_2) groups, do not neighboring with methine (CH) group in alkyl compounds; methylene (CH_2) group in cycle
37.0–60.0	methine (CH) group in alkyl fragments; CH and CH_2 alkyl groups of naphthenic fragments, adjacent to CH group
108.0–118.0	olefin fragments
118.0–129.5	protonated arenes
129.5–133.0	internal aromatic carbon atoms
133.0–135.0	methyl substituted arenes
135.0–138.0	arenes, substituted by naphthenes
138.0–160.0	alkyl substituted (except for methyl substituted) arenes; heteroatomic (N, O, S) arenes
165.0–175.0	ester or amide carboxy carbon atom
170.0–182.0	acid carboxy carbon atom
182.0–192.0	quinone carboxy carbon atom
195.0–205.0	aldehyde carbonyl carbon atom
202.0–220.0	ketone carbonyl carbon atom

Information obtained by integration of aromatic signals in individual spectral ranges is represented by the fraction of the corresponding carbon atoms relative to their total number. Fraction of aromatic carbons C_{ar} can be straightforwardly found from NMR spectra:

$$C_{\text{ar}} = \frac{I_{\text{ar}}}{\sum_j I_j}, \quad (1)$$

where C_{ar} is the fraction of aromatic carbons, I_{ar} is the total integral intensity of aromatic carbons, and I_j is

the integral intensity of all functional groups in the ^{13}C NMR spectrum of the sample.

It is impossible to obtain unambiguous information on the content of hydrocarbons (alkanes, cyclanes) from ^{13}C NMR spectra, although this information is contained in the fragmentary composition,

$$C_t = ((1.04I_t - 0.034I_{sq}) / (I_t + I_{sq} + I_p))(1 - C_{ar}), \quad (2)$$

$$C_p = ((1.02I_p - 0.006I_{sq}) / (I_t + I_{sq} + I_p))(1 - C_{ar}), \quad (3)$$

$$C_{sq} = ((1.04I_{sq} - 0.04I_t - 0.02I_p) / (I_t + I_{sq} + I_p))(1 - C_{ar}), \quad (4)$$

where C_t is the fraction of tertiary carbons; C_p , fraction of primary carbons; C_{sq} , fraction of secondary and quaternary carbons; I_t is the total integral intensity of tertiary (CH) groups; I_{sq} , total integral intensity of secondary (CH₂) and quaternary groups; I_p , total integral intensity of primary (CH₃) groups in ^{13}C NMR spectrum of the oil sample.

Mean chain length (MCL) was calculated as:

$$\text{MCL} = 2 * \left(\frac{C_{sq} + C_t}{C_p} \right) + 2 \quad (5)$$

which can be determined with high accuracy. If integral intensities of individual group signals in the ^{13}C NMR spectrum are known, then corresponding molar fractions of tertiary, primary, secondary and quaternary carbons can be calculated by the following formulas:

The aromaticity factor (F_{CA}) can be calculated from the equation:

$$F_{CA} = \frac{C_{ar}}{C_{ar} + C_{al}}, \quad (6)$$

where $C_{al} = C_p + C_{sq} + C_t$ is the total aliphatic carbon content.

Estimation of molar fractions C_p , C_{sq} , C_t , C_{ar} and the aromaticity factor (F_{CA}), and mean chain length (MCL) by integration of the corresponding areas of ^{13}C NMR spectra was carried out in a way similar to our previous works ([18, 12-18]; [19, 256-262]; [20, 995]) (Table 2).

Table 2.

Molar fractions (%) of primary (C_p), secondary and quaternary (C_{sq}), tertiary (C_t), aromatic (C_{ar}) groups, aromaticity factor (F_{CA}) and mean chain length (MCL) of aliphatic hydrocarbons of light, heavy and catalyzed oil samples based on ^{13}C NMR spectra.

Group type	Relative molar content, %		
	light oil	heavy oil	catalyzed oil (Ni-Co, Al ₂ O ₃)
C_p	25.8	12.0	18.5
C_{sq}	53.0	46.2	55.4
C_t	10.0	12.6	10.8
C_{ar}	12.5	29.2	15.3
F_{CA}	0.123	0.292	0.155
MCL	6.9	11.8	7.5

Based on obtained data (Table 2), we can see that the highest percentage of primary and secondary/quaternary carbons is in light oil sample, which is however almost twice as low in the content of aromatic carbons. The twofold excess of the relative content of aromatic carbon in heavy oil sample compared with light oil sample is observed. The catalytic treatment of heavy oil leads to the fact that it approaches light oil in its structural-group characteristics. A decrease in the aromaticity factor (F_{CA}) and the average length of the hydrocarbon chain (MCL) also indicate about the success of the catalytic treatment of the studied heavy oil sample. Thus there is a mutually inverse dependency for primary and aromatic carbons as the viscosity of the studied samples changes.

4. Detailed description and comparison of ^{13}C NMR spectra of light, heavy and catalyzed oils by NMR spectroscopy data

Based on the above equations, it follows that the assignment of signals in the ^{13}C NMR spectra is important. In this work, we set ourselves the goal to the detailed assignment of these NMR signals and their comparison depending on the viscosity of the sample and also observe directly in the change in specific signals in the NMR spectrum by the effect of catalytic treatment.

^{13}C NMR spectra of three oil samples (light, heavy, catalyzed) were detailed analyzed and the assignment of all signals were carried out. The aromatic area of ^{13}C NMR spectra of studied oils with enumerated peaks are presented in Figs. 1,2.

To distinguish between secondary (CH₂) and tertiary (CH) hydrocarbon groups ^{13}C NMR Attached Proton Test (APT), and ^{13}C NMR Gated Decoupling (GD) experiments were applied, similar to our previous work [21, 269-274].

Fig. 1. The aromatic area of ^{13}C NMR spectra of light, heavy and catalyzed oils.

There is a characteristic broader broadening in the aromatic area of the spectrum for heavy oil, but the number of separately distinguishable signals is already less than for the light oil sample. However, in this case, signals in the highly aromatic area ($1'-5'$) related to the carboxy groups (COOH) of the carbon atom are clearly visible. Also in the sample of heavy oil, signals from carbon atoms with a double bond in the presence of heteroatoms are observed ($6'-8'$). And their number is three times less compared to the light oil sample (1-10). For the catalyzed sample, we were able to clearly identify signals only for protonated carbon atoms ($1''-4''$).

And it turned out that their number is two times less than for a sample of heavy oil ($9'-16'$) and three times less than for a sample of light oil (11-22). It is also noticeable that a still rather strong broadening is retained in the aromatic region of the spectrum of the sample treated with the catalyst. Although the overall integration of this area and the structural group analysis show a noticeable decrease in the proportion of aromatic carbons for the catalyzed sample compared to the heavy oil sample. This proves that the catalyst does a good job of reducing the viscosity of the oil.

Fig. 2. The aliphatic area of ^{13}C NMR spectra of light, heavy and catalyzed oils.

In Fig. 2 presented the signals of ^{13}C nuclei and their chemical shifts for studied samples. In a heavy oil sample, fewer signals from ^{13}C nuclei are observed compared to samples of heavy oil and catalyzed oil. Moreover, as can be seen from the Fig. 2, the signals in

the NMR spectrum of catalyzed oil appear more clearly and are similar in shape to signals in a sample of light oil. There is also a decrease in the signals of carbon CH_3 groups in the catalyzed oil sample. All these facts together with the molar fraction data above prove that the

use of a catalyst is very effective for upgrading oil and improving the quality of fuel.

5. Conclusions

The structural-group characteristics of three oil samples (light, heavy, catalyzed) are compared and a detailed assignment of the chemical shifts of ^{13}C nuclei in the ^{13}C NMR spectra is carried out. A decrease in the aromaticity factor and the average length of the hydrocarbon chain indicate about the success of the catalytic treatment of the studied heavy oil sample. A mutually inverse dependency for primary and aromatic carbons as the viscosity of the studied samples changes is observed. Detailed assignment of the ^{13}C NMR signals and their comparison depending on the viscosity of the sample is carried out and the changes in specific signals in the NMR spectrum by the effect of catalytic treatment are fixed.

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